

SOUTH THAILAND STUDENT'S IDIOLECT OF MALAY LANGUAGE INTO INDONESIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This study aims to describe and analyze South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language who studied at Muhammadiyah University of Tangerang. The data in this study is the formation of new idiolect language in Indonesian language vocabulary terms. This study has two types of data, primary data and secondary data. Primary data in this study are original data obtained by direct interviews. Meanwhile, secondary data in this study are book references related to the object of the research. This study uses a qualitative research. Data collection techniques in this study are observation, interview and documentation techniques. The method used in this study is content analysis method. From this research, it was found that the process of South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language in general is a simplification of the language form of morphology, syntax, various phonology, and reduction.

Keywords: South Thailand Student's Idiolect, Malay Language, Indonesian Language

INTRODUCTION

In this social life, Humans need a language to be used as a medium or tool to communicate in everyday life. Various kinds of languages vary widely, but among members of the language community can interact and understand each other because they use relatively the same linguistic forms when they are speaking. The difference in language use in one social group is certainly different from others. There are two possibilities that makes it happen: First, that the two social groups still understand each other's different languages. Second, in the other hand they don't understand each other. If the first fact happens it means that they are still in one speech community, but if the second fact happens, then they are in a different speech society.

The level of education, age, gender and occupation are important factors that affect language variations in language societies. The language used by a teacher will be different from the language used by a worker. This is because the level of education and type of work of a teacher is higher than a worker. This is different from the language used by a student from Thailand who studied and lived in Indonesia for more than two years. Basically, in the first period the language that they used was still not perfect. However, after developing social relations and interactions with their colleagues, the language they use has gradually improved even though the pronunciation or idiolect they used in communicating are still unclear.

Social interaction exists because of the speaking activities of language-speaking members. Speech activity will be successful when it is supported by several factors such as good social interaction, written and oral expression, and without those activities, the language will disappear because there is no speaking activity in society

In sociolinguistic studies there is always a relationship between society and language, therefore in sociolinguistic studies, it actually will discuss the phonological problem of Thai Students when they are communicating with Indonesian community in Indonesia, are their language and pronunciation good or not Thai we need to first understand the Thai people when communicating with the Indonesian community while in Indonesia. The language and pronunciation are good or not. So we need to discuss first the sociolinguistics. According to Sumarsono (2007) sociolinguistics is an institutional linguistic that is related to the linked language with people who use the language itself. (p.2) Sumarsono defined that sociolinguistics is a field of linguistics that deals with language with someone who uses the language where it is used itself. Wijana (2006) argues that sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that places the position of language in relation to language users in society. (p. 7). Wijana argued the sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that places the position of language in the relationship of language users in a particular society. According to Rafiek (2005) that sociolinguistics is a study of language in its implementation aims to study how conventions on the relation of language use for social aspects, in the other word Rafiek said that sociolinguistics teaches the use of language relations for social aspects.

Based on the three experts above, it can be concluded that sociolinguistics is an interdisciplinary science between sociology and linguistics, the two closely related empirical studies that both of them are about study of language in relation to the use of that language in society.

Every activity that is scientific certainly has an object. Likewise with linguistics, which takes language as its object because there are also other disciplines that make language its "side object" so it is better to talk about what language is, so that it can be understood the correlation between linguistics and other discipline study.

According to Mahmudah (2011) language is a system of sound symbols used by members of social groups to work together, communicate, and identify themselves. (p. 1). Mahmudah defines language is a system of sound symbols that has specific characteristics and is not shared by other languages, in this language it is usually used by certain groups in its use within the community. Chaer (2010) states that language is a system, means that language is formed by a number of components that are permanently patterned and can be addressed (p. 11). He defines that it can be concluded that language is a system that has certain differences in each region, but even though different languages remain the same pattern using the national language, namely using Indonesian.

In accordance with Kushartanti (2009), it is stated that language is defined as a sound sign system agreed to be used by members of certain community groups in working together, communicating, and identifying themselves (p. 3). Kushartanti agreed that language is called the sound sign system used in certain areas, namely to communicate with certain groups of people and to identify themselves in communicating well.

So from the three experts above, it can be concluded that language is a system of arbitrary sound symbols used by members of social groups in communicating as the most prominent

different aspect, because through language each social group will feel as a different unit from other groups. Therefore, language is very beautiful when it is combined with various languages in other regions, with language we can understand the various social groups that use the language.

Other aspect of language in society is phonology. As a science, phonology is divided into phonetics and phonemic. In general, ordinary phonetics is described as a branch of the study of phonology that studies the sounds of language without paying attention to whether these sounds have a function to distinguish meaning or not. Meanwhile, phonemic is a branch of the study of phonology that studies the sounds of language by paying attention to the function of these sounds as distinguishing meanings. The following is the definition of phonology according to experts: According to Abdullah (2013) phonology is a field of linguistics that studies, discusses, talks, and analyzes language sounds produced by human speech instruments. (p. 51) Abdullah's intention is that phonology is a field science that discusses bunny i-language sounds produced by human speech tools.

Based on the experts above, it can be concluded that phonology is a branch of linguistics that studies language sounds in human speech tools based on their function or usage in a pronunciation that will discuss idiolect.

Idiolect is a variety of language that is unique to an individual. This is manifested by a pattern of choice of vocabulary or idioms (individual lexicons), grammar, or pronunciation that is unique to each person. So, everyone has their own idiolect. These linguistic characteristics include linguistic aspects, these characteristics form an identity that is inherent in the speakers, for example in the university circumstances there are various kinds of local people who study at the Muhammadiyah University of Tangerang and some of them even came from abroad such as Thailand. Certainly it is very easy to know and analyze the idiolectal language they use when interacting, the Idiolect are different when they speak.

Based on the experts above, it can be concluded that idiolect is a variation of the language or characteristic of a person with regard to the color of the voice so that we can find out by listening to his voice while speaking without seeing the person, we can immediately recognize the person easily.

As mentioned by Horwich (2020) besides communal languages (such as Swahili, Hindi, Mandarin, Arabic, and even Indonesian), we should acknowledge the existence of idiolects that are developed by the individual members of linguistic communities where the meaning of a word in a communal language is constructed from the somewhat different meanings it has within the different idiolects of the speakers of that language.

Another research that has been done by Widagdo and friends (2019) that idiolect can be found in the dialogue in literature especially in Wayang Purwa that idiolect was used to describe every specific individual's speech and character in that literature.

The term idiolect refers to the unique and distinctive use of language of an individual, it can be either in writing and speaking. Perifanos and friends (2019) wrote their paper that

focused on idiolect of learning distributed representations (embeddings) of social media users that reflect their writing style.

Therefore, the similarity aspect of idiolect in Perifanos' paper and Widagdo will not be the main focus of this research, it is not writing aspect and literature, this research focused on speaking. Furthermore, here the objective of this research is to describe and analyze the South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language in the language form of morphology, syntax, various phonology, reduction and reduction, and word borrowing from several languages.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with content analysis methods. a type of research that seeks to describe problem solving without going through statistical procedures or any form of calculation. Qualitative research method is a way or more efforts to focus on the aspect of understanding in depth on a problem. Qualitative research is also called descriptive research, it tends to use analysis and emphasizes the process of meaning. The technique of collecting data used in this study is speech method or interview. In this method, the researcher uses the basic technique in speech method is the fishing technique, in this technique the researcher uses advanced techniques, because the researcher has a direct conversation by dealing directly with the informant or the source.

Researchers observed and analyzed the results of data collection using the extralingual equivalent method, which is in this method. Researchers examined pronunciation (phonology) when Thai students speak using Indonesian language. By using interview method, the researcher can find out the developments that have occurred among the resources, the student from Thailand. So researchers can compare and analyze the development of Thai students in their communication.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the research that has been done that analyzes South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language, the researcher conducted an interview with two Thai students from the Indonesian Language and Literature Education Study Program, they are in fifth semester Zulkiflee baka alee and Nurhafaeda Thoh.

The result of the interview has been done with Zulkiflee baka alee:

Seperti = Sepeti

Error found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Due to the omission of consonant phonemes, namely the phoneme / r / in word "seperti", so that they are pronounced "sepeti". So, the standard word is "seperti" not "sepeti". In KBBI the word "seperti" means similar, but a word "sepeti" even though it is only one letter is omitted, it will mean a heavy load on an object. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word.

Sedikit = Dikit.

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Due to the omission of consonant phonemes. Namely the phoneme / s / and vowel / e / in a word “sedikit” , so that it is pronounced as “dikit”, whereas the standard word is “sedikit” not ”dikit”. The word “sedikit” in KBBI means not much.

Senang = Seneng.

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Because the change between the words “senang” into “seneng”. From the word happy, it means that there is a change from vowel / a / to vowel / e /. The standard word in Indonesian should be “senang” not “seneng”. The word “senang” in KBBI is satisfied, without feeling sad and disappointed.

Bahagia = Bahagio.

Errors at the phonological level are pronunciation errors. Due to a change in vowels. Namely from vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / o /. So, in the word “bahagia”, there is a change that should be well spoken in Indonesian, “bahagia”, not “bahagio”. The word happy in KBBI means a state or feeling of being happy.

Penyampaiannya = Penyampaiannye.

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Because there is a change in the vowel of the vowel phoneme / a / to the vowel phoneme / e /. So in the word “Penyampaiannya” there is a change in the vowel phoneme / a / into / o /. So the standard words in Indonesian is “Penyampaiannya” not “Penyampaiannye“. The meaning of the word “Penyampaiannya” is taken from the word up to KBBI which means reaching. If interpreted the word convey is an idea or thoughts of someone who is delivered orally or in writing.

Penggunaan = Peggunaan

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Because there is a reduction in the consonant phoneme / n / in the word usage. So, the standard word in Indonesian should be “Peggunaan”. The word “Peggunaan” is taken from the word “guna”, which means in KBBI benefit.

Banyak = Banya

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Because there is a consonant reduction in the phoneme / k / in the word “Banyak”. So, the standard word in Indonesian should be “Banyak”, not “Banya”. The meaning of the word “Banyak” in KBBI is a large number.

Bapak = Pa.

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “Bapak”. So, the standard word in Indonesian should be “Bapak”, not “Pa”. The meaning of the word “Bapak” denotes a male parent. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word.

Semangat = Semanget

The error is found at the phonological level, namely pronunciation errors. Due to a change in vowels, namely vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / e /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Semangat”, not “Semangat”. Because the word “Semangat” means the spirit of life that animates the heart, both life and death. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word.

The result of the interview has been done with Nurhafaeda Thoh.

Baik = Bae

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “baik” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “baik”, not “bae”. In KBBI, good means beautiful, obedient, meanwhile “bae” has no meaning. Except in Betawi, the word bae has a function as a variation or complement to the language. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Indonesia = Indonesa

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Indonesia” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the vowel phoneme / i /. So the standard word of Indonesia is “Indonesia” not “Indonesa”.

Pengalaman = Pengalama

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Pengalaman” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / n /. So the standard word in Indonesia is “Pengalaman” not “Pengalama”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Beberapa = Beberapao

Errors at the phonological level of the word “Beberapa” are pronunciation errors. Due to the change of vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / o /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Beberapa” not “Beberapao”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Tahun = Tahu

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Tahun”, namely pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / n /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Tahun” not “Tahu”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Terhadap = Terhada

Errors at the phonological level of the word “Terhadap”, namely pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / p /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Terhadap”, not “Terhada”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Keluarga = Keluarage

Errors that exist at the phonological level of the word “Keluarga” are pronunciation errors. Due

to the change of vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / e /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “keluarga”, not “keluarage”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Masuk = Masu

Errors that are found at the phonological level of the word “Masuk” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k / in the incoming word. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Masuk”, not “masu”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Mengajarkan = Mengajarka

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Mengajarkan” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / n / in the word “Mengajarkan”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Mengajarkan” not “Mengajarka”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Dosen = Dose

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Dosen” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / n / in the word “Dosen”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Dosen” not “Dose”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Pak = Pa

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Pak” are spelling errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “Pak”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Pak” not “Pa”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Mengajarnya = Mengajarnya

Errors that are found at the phonological level of the word “Mengajarnya” are pronunciation errors. Due to the change of vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / o /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Mengajarnya” not “Mengajarnya”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Mempunyai = mempunya’i

Errors that are found at the phonological level of the word “Mempunyai” are pronunciation error of the letter / i / separately, because they are accustomed to pronouncing words having the phoneme / i / separately which they pronounce. Meanwhile it must be pronounced by “mempunyai” rather than “mempunya’i”.

Tersendiri = Tersendire

Error that occurs at the phonological level of the word “Tersendiri”, namely in pronunciation. Due to the change of vowel phoneme / i / to vowel phoneme / e /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Tersendiri” not “Tersendire”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the

meaning of the word meaning.

Bervariasi = Bervarias'i

Errors that are found at the phonological level of the word “bervariasi” are pronunciation error of the letter / i / separately, because they are accustomed to pronouncing words having the phoneme / i / separately which they pronounce. Meanwhile it must be pronounced by “bervariasi” rather than “bervarias'i”.

Banyak = Banya

Errors that exist at the phonological level of the word “banyak” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “banyak”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “banyak” not “banyak”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word

Nasi Goreng = Nasi goeng

Errors that exist at the phonological level of the word “Nasi Goreng” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / r / in the word “goreng”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Nasi Goreng” not “Nasi Goeng”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Bakso = Ba'so

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Bakso” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “bakso”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “bakso” not “ba'so”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Menangkap = menangkap

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “menangkap”, namely pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “Menangkap”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “menangkap” not “menangkap”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Lewat = Lewa

Errors found at the phonological level of the word “Lewat” are pronunciation errors. Due to the reduction of the phoneme / t / in the word “lewat”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “lewat” not “lewa”. Because if one letter is different, it will affect the meaning of the word meaning.

Futhermore, here researchers analyzed the data from the interviews that have been done to those South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into indonesian language based on phonological change and it's analysis.

The data analysis of Zulkiflee baka alee for South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language

No	Phonological Change	Words	Pronunciations	Explanations
1	/r/	[Seperti]	[Sepeti]	The omission of consonant phonemes, namely the phoneme / r / in word "seperti", so that they are pronounced "sepeti". So, the standard word is "seperti" not "sepeti".
2	/s/ - /e/	[Sedikit]	[Dikit]	The omission of consonant phonemes. Namely the phoneme / s / and vowel / e / in a word "sedikit", so that it is pronounced as "dikit", whereas the standard word is "sedikit" not "dikit".
3	/a/ - /e/	[Senang]	[Seneng]	The change between the words "senang" into "seneng". From the word happy, it means that there is a change from vowel / a / to vowel / e /. The standard word in Indonesian should be "senang" not "seneng".
4	/a/ - /e/	[Bahagia]	[Bahagio]	A change in vowels. Namely from vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / o /. So, in the word "bahagia", there is a change that should be well spoken in Indonesian, "bahagia", not "bahagio".
5	/a/ - /e/	[Penyampaiannya]	[Penyampaiannya]	There is a change in the vowel of the vowel phoneme / a / to the vowel phoneme / e /. So in the word "Penyampaiannya" there is a change in the vowel phoneme / a / into / o /. So the standard words in Indonesian is "Penyampaiannya" not "Penyampaiannya".
6	/k/	[Banyak]	[Banya]	There is a reduction in the consonant phoneme / n / in the word usage. So, the standard word in Indonesian should be "Penggunaan".
7	/n/	[Penggunaan]	[Pengguna]	There is a consonant reduction in the phoneme / k / in the word "Banyak". So, the standard word in Indonesian should be "Banyak", not "Banya".
8	/k/	[Bapak]	[bapa]	The reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word "Bapak". So, the standard word in Indonesian should be "Bapak", not "Pa".
9	/a/ - /e/	[Semangat]	[Semanget]	To a change in vowels, namely vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / e /. So the standard word in Indonesian is "Semangat", not "Semanget".

The data analysis of Nurhafaeda Thoh for South Thailand student's idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language

No	Phonological Change	Words	Pronunciations	Explanations
1	/k/	[Baik]	[Bae]	The reduction of the phoneme / k /. so the standard word in Indonesian is "baik", not "bae"
2	/i/	[Indonesia]	[Indonesa]	The reduction of the vowel phoneme / i /. so the standard word of Indonesia is "Indonesia" not "Indonesa".
3	/n/	[Pengalaman]	[pengalama]	The reduction of the phoneme / n /. So the standard word in Indonesia is "Pengalaman" not "Pengalama".
4	/a/ - /o/	[Beberapa]	[Beberapo]	Karena adanya perubahan fonem vokal /a/ menjadi fonem vokal /o/. jadi kata baku dalam bahasa Indonesia itu adalah Beberapa bukan Beberapo
5	/n/	[Tahun]	[Tahu]	The reduction of the phoneme / n /. so the standard word in Indonesian is "Tahun" not "Tahu".
6	/p/	[Terhadap]	[Terhada]	The reduction of the phoneme / p /. so the standard word in Indonesian is "Terhadap", not "Terhada".
7	/a/ - /e/	[Keluarga]	[Keluarge]	The change of vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / e /. so the standard word in Indonesian is "keluarga", not "keluarge".
8	/k/	[Masuk]	[Masu]	The reduction of the phoneme / k / in the incoming word. so the standard word in Indonesian is "Masuk", not "masu".
9	/n/	[Mengajarkan]	[Mengajarka]	The reduction of the phoneme / n / in the word "Mengajarkan". So the standard word in Indonesian is "Mengajarkan" not "Mengajarka".
10	/n/	[Dosen]	[Dose]	The reduction of the phoneme / n / in the word "Dosen". So the standard word in Indonesian is "Dosen" not "Dose".
11	/k/	[Pak]	[Pa]	The reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word "Pak". So the standard word in Indonesian is "Pak" not "Pa".
12	/a/ - /o/	[Mengajarnya]	[Mengajarnya]	The change of vowel phoneme / a / to vowel phoneme / o /. So the standard word in Indonesian is "Mengajarnya" not "Mengajarnya".
13	/i/	[Mempunyai]	[mempunya'i]	Errors that are found at the phonological level of the word "Mempunyai" are pronunciation error of the letter / i / separately, because they are accustomed to pronouncing words having the phoneme / i / separately which they pronounce. Meanwhile it must be pronounced by "mempunyai" rather than "mempunya'i".
14	/i/ - /e/	[Tersendiri]	[Tersendire]	Error that occurs at the phonological level of the word "Tersendiri", namely in pronunciation. Due

				to the change of vowel phoneme / i / to vowel phoneme / e /. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Tersendiri” not “Tersendire”.
15	/i/	[Bervariasi]	[Bervarias'i]	Errors that are found at the phonological level of the word “bervariasi” are pronunciation error of the letter / i / separately, because they are accustomed to pronouncing words having the phoneme / i / separately which they pronounce. Meanwhile it must be pronounced by “bervariasi” rather than “bervarias'i”.
16	/k/	[Banyak]	[Banya]	The reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “banyak”. so the standard word in Indonesian is “banyak” not “banya”.
17	/r/	[Nasi Goreng]	[Nasi Goeng]	The reduction of the phoneme / r / in the word “goreng”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “Nasi Goreng” not “Nasi Goeng”..
18	/k/	[Bakso]	[Ba'so]	The reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “bakso”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “bakso” not “ba'so”
19	/k/	[Menangkap]	[menangap]	The reduction of the phoneme / k / in the word “Menangkap”. so the standard word in Indonesian is “menangkap” not “menangap”..
20	/t/	[Lewat]	[Lewa]	The reduction of the phoneme / t / in the word “lewat”. So the standard word in Indonesian is “lewat” not “lewa”..

From this research, after conducting analysis it was found that the process of South Thailand student’s idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language in general is a simplification of the language form of morphology, syntax, various phonology, and reduction

CONCLUSION

The results of the research that the researchers have done, entitled Analysis South Thailand Student’s Idiolect of Malay Language into Indonesian Language. Researchers found a problem from the results of interviews between the two South Thailand students from the fifth semester of class A2 Indonesian language and literature education, they are Zulkiflee Baka Alee and Nurhafeda Thoh. From the research results of the two students, their daily pronunciation of Indonesian is good enough. However, from a linguistic point of view, especially the phonology, it is still not good. Especially Nurhafeda Thoh.

In terms of pronunciation in speaking using Indonesian Language, it seems that Nurhafeda Thoh feels difficult to express it. Sometimes she still stuttered even though in written form, even using sign language to communicate when talking to his friends when she didn't understand what she wanted to say. Meanwhile, Zulkiflee Baka Alee is good enough in daily communication and has started to master his Indonesian language. Even the level in phonology is starting to be good. It's just that it needs to be developed more in pronunciation. This is because Zulkiflee' Baka Alee often hangs out with friends around him, while Nurhafeda Thoh lacks interaction with classmates, and still hangs out with colleagues from Thailand. And the

main process of their idiolect of Malay language into Indonesian language in general is a simplification of the language form of morphology, syntax, various phonology, and reduction.

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References

- 1) Arianti,R. (2022). Improvement of Novel Review Text Skills Throught Think Talk Write Model In Smp Negeri 3 Rambah (Peningkatan Keterampilan Menulis Teks Ulasan Novel Melalui Model Think Talk Write Di SMP Negeri 3 Rambah.Vol.6.No.1 April 2020. (29-38). http://ejournal.stkip-pgri-sumbar.ac.id/index.php/jurnal_gramatika/article/view/3401/pdf
- 2) Chaer, Abdul dan Agustina, Leonie. (2017). Sosiolinguistik Perkenalan Awal. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 3) Chaer, Abdul. (2022)). Kajian Bahasa. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- 4) Chaer, Abdul. (2015). Linguistik Umum. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- 5) Damayanti, Rini dan Inrayanti, Tri. (2015). Bahasa Indonesia. Surabaya:Victory Inti Opta
- 6) Djonnaidi Silvia. Language Change in Oral Culture in Minangkabau Society: A Diachronic Study. Vol.6 No.1 April 2020. (118-137). Gramatika. Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia STKIP PGRI Sumbar. http://ejournal.stkip-pgri-sumbar.ac.id/index.php/jurnal_gramatika/article/view/3401/pdf
- 7) Horwich P. (2022) Languages and Idiolects. In: Bianchi A. (eds) Language and Reality from a Naturalistic Perspective. Philosophical Studies Series, vol 142. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-47641-0_14
- 8) Hasmawati. Mantasiah, R. Yusri. (2020). Acontrastive Analysis of the Use of Prepositi0ns in German and Indonesian. Eralingua Journal Pendidikan Bahasa asing dan Sastra Vol.4. No.1. 2020. <https://ojs.unm.ac.id/eralingua>.
- 9) HP, Achmad dan Abdullah, Alek. (2016). Linguistik Umum. Jakarta: Erlangga
- 10) Kartikasari, Ratna Dewi. (2019). Penggunaan Bilingualisme pada Masyarakat yang Berwirausaha. Bahasa dan Sastra. Universitas Muhammadiyah Jakarta. No. 1 Vol 2 Th 2019 hal 212-219
- 11) Karina. F.L.S. Sunarti.Aiga.V. (2020). Contrastive Study of Chinese and Indonesia Passive Sentences. Eralingua Journal Pendidikan Bahasa asing dan Sastra Vol.4. No.2. 2020. <https://ojs.unm.ac.id/eralingua>.
- 12) Konstantinos, P, Eirini, F, Dionysis,GA. (2020). Word embeddings for idiolect identification. Department of Linguistics, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
- 13) Kushartanti dkk. (2005). Pesona Bahasa: Langkah Awal Memahami Linguistik. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 14) Mahmudah dan Ghani. A. (2015). Disiplin Berbahasa Indonesia. Jakarta: FITK Press.
- 15) Mar'at, Samsunuwiyati. (2017). Psikolinguistik. Bandung: PT. Refika Agitama
- 16) Muslich, Masnur. (2023). Fonologi Bahasa Indonesia. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- 17) Mutoharoh.M.,Sulaeman.,A.& Goziyah.G.(2018). Interferensi Morfologi dalam Karangan Narasi

- Mahasiswa Thailand Semester IV Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia FKIP Universitas Muhammadiyah Tangerang. *Silampari Bisa: Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Bahasa Indonesia Daerah dan Asing*. 1(1).85.doi.0.31540/Silimparibisa.v1i1.10
- 18) Satomi, Arisha. (2018). *Integrasi Bahasa Inggris Ke Bahasa Indonesia Berbasis*
 - 19) *Media Komunikasi Elektronik Komputer*. Universitas Muhammadiyah
 - 20) Surakarta. (<http://eprints.ums.ac.id/65101/2/NASKAH%20PUBLIKASI.pdf>)
 - 21) Suherman, A., & Sulaeman, A. (2020). Bilingualism in *Gadis Pantai Novel* by Pramoedya Ananta Toer. *Journal of English Education and Teaching*, 4(2), 264- 277
 - 22) Sukmadinata, Nana Syaodih. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
 - 23) Sulaeman, Agus dan Goziah. (2019). *Metodologi Penelitian Bahasa dan Sastra*. Jakarta: Edu Pustaka
 - 24) Sulaeman, A. Zainal, R. Aceng, R. (2018). *Mantra Structure of Banten and Its Implication in Literary Learning*. Vol.4 No.1. 2018. <http://ejournal.stkip-pgri-sumbar.ac.id/index.php/jurnal-gramatika/index>
 - 25) Sulaeman.A. Goziah, Ira.AP.Noermanzah. *Social Value in the Novel Hatta: Aku Datang Karena Sejarah* by Sergius Sutanto as Teaching Material in Teaching Literature in School. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. Vol.9 issue 3.March 2020. <https://www.ijstr.org>.
 - 26) Sulaeman, A. (2022). *Structure of Sunda in Tangerang Regency and the Territory of Use*. Vol. 3. No. 1. *Journal Indonesian Language Education and Literature*. (ILEAL).
 - 27) Sulaeman, A. (2021). *Bahasa Slang Generasi Muda dalam Media Sosial di Era Milenial*. In *Seminar Nasional Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra* (pp. 45-54).
 - 28) Widagdo, Titis Bayu and, Djatmika and Yustanto, Henry, *Idiolect 'Antawacana' Werkudara in Wayang Purwa* (2019). *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Translation (IJLLT)*, 2020, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3546849>